

1 **ECT2 expression is correlated with solid tumor diameter (size), and this is in part a function of its**
2 **role in an asymmetric cell division program.**

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7 A direct relationship between ECT2 expression and solid tumor size (diameter), and its co-regulation in a
8 transcriptional network with genes functioning in asymmetric cell division suggests its function as a
9 component of the solid tumor gene expression program is related to a mechanism by which solid tumor
10 utilize asymmetric cell division programs that integrate programs utilized by stem cells and the oocyte to
11 balance self renewal versus daughter cell division.

12 Citations

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16 cellular transformation. *Oncogene*, 28(41), pp.3597-3607.